

OPTIMIZATION OF BETULIN EXTRACTION FROM BIRCH BARK

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doctor of philosophy in chemistry (PhD)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7870311>

Betulin (betulinol, Birch camphor, lupendiol) is a lupan-type five-ring triterpene alcohol. It is found in birch and oak bark, in the composition of the chinese zizyphys plant, kalindula, maple, white poplar and other medicinal plants up to 3-35% [1]. Betulin, chemical name 3β , 28-dihydroxy-20 (29)-lupene ($C_{30}H_{50}O_2$) is a crystalline organic compound with a molecular mass of – 442, ranging from light yellow – to 97% purity betulin, to white – to 99% purity betulin. The liquefaction temperature ranges from 251°C to 257°C. Acetone, Tetrahydrofuran, dimethylsulfoxide, is well soluble in hot chloroform, poorly soluble in other organic solvents, completely insoluble in water [2]. Odorless, tasteless, stable, inert, non-toxic substance.

A great deal of research has been done on the extraction of betulin with various organic solvents, notably ethanol, benzene, diethyl ether, dichloromethane and acetone [3].

White birch bark contains substances with high biological activity, and depending on the type, leaf and growth conditions of the tree, age, the content of betulin in the bark varies in the range from 10% to 40% [3-4]. Taking into account this, we isolated the substance betulin from the composition of white birch bark growing on the territory of Uzbekistan using the extraction method using various solvents.

Table 1

Extraction of betulin from white birch using various solvents

Solvent	Extraction time (h)	The amount of peel obtained (g)	The amount of substance extracted	
			g	%
Ethanol	3	10	3.6	36
Propanol	3	10	1.7	17
Acetone	3	10	2.8	28
Hexane	3	10	1.9	19
Butanol 2	3	10	1.75	17.5
Isobutyl alcohol	3	10	1.4	14
Butanol 1	3	10	1.1	11

Among different solvents, it was found that betulin extraction yield is higher using ethanol [5]. After finding the optimal solvent, the dependence of the

extraction process yield on various other factors (solvent concentration, solvent amount, extraction time) was studied. The following results were obtained.

Table 2

Dependence of betulin extraction on extraction time

Solvent	Extraction time (h)	The amount of peel obtained (g)	The amount of substance extracted	
			g	%
Ethanol	2	10	2.95	29.5
	2.5	10	3.2	32
	3	10	3.6	36
	3.5	10	3.0	30
	4	10	2.9	29

As can be seen from the above data, the optimal extraction time for the extraction of betulin substance was 3 hours. After finding the optimal time, we studied the extraction yield also depends on the amount of solvent used. In this case, ethanol, which is considered the optimal solvent, was taken in different amounts compared to the obtained bark, and we carried out the extraction process at the same time. The results were as follows.

Table 3

Dependence of betulin extraction on the amount of solvent

Solvent	Solvent volume (ml)	The amount of peel obtained (g)	The amount of substance extracted	
			g	%
Ethanol	150	10	2.6	26
	175	10	2.7	27
	200	10	3.6	36
	225	10	3.2	32
	250	10	3.0	30

Based on the obtained results, it can be concluded that the best solvent for extracting betulin from white birch bark was ethanol, the optimal amount of solvent was 200 ml, and the time was 3 hours.

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